

Reaction of GLH-resistant rices to RTV complex when inoculated with different numbers of viruliferous GLH per plant.

infection. ASD7 had severe yellowing and stunting but high RTBV infection.

Results indicate there are two types of RTV resistance

- high resistance to RTBV + RTSV

and RTBV alone even with high insect pressure, and

- increasing RTBV infection with increased insect pressure.

In the latter case, however, infected

varieties may not be a virus source for the spread of the disease. Furthermore, resistance to RTV complex is not always correlated with resistance to the vector, as shown by Habiganj DW8. *ℵ*

Rice gall dwarf virus (GDV) outbreak in West Guangdong Province, China

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In 1981, an unknown rice disease occurred on 7,3 10 ha in West Guangdong. By 1982, the disease had spread to 33,333 ha. Disease incidence was 30-40% and caused losses of 1.9 to 4.5 t/ha. Symptoms were stunting, dark green leaves, small light green galls on leaf blades and sheaths, and low tillering. Hybrid rices Shan You I, Shan

You 2, Shan You 6, and Shan You 30 were very susceptible, as were some local varieties.

Electron microscopy showed that polyhedral particles 60 nm in diameter were associated with the diseased plants. *Recilia dorsalis* (Motsch), *Nephotettix*

cincticeps (Uhler), and *N. virescens* (Distant) transmitted the disease. Based on the characteristic gall, size of the virus particles, and vectors, the disease was considered to be GDV, which occurs in Thailand and Malaysia. *ℵ*

Breakdown of Xa 4 gene for resistance to bacterial blight (BB) at Pantnagar, India

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BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* is a major disease of rice in

the tarai belt of Uttar Pradesh, where it causes up to 80% yield losses. Incidence is increasing, and in 1982 and 1983 some previously resistant varieties were infected.

To identify reliable donors of resistance against the Pantnagar race of the pathogen, we artificially field-screened 101 entries, including international differentials for BB, promising IRRI varieties, elite strains